

APPLICATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE GARMENT INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT.

The article substantiates the importance of information technology in the preparation of production of sewing enterprises. The computer-aided clothing design systems available on the market help to effectively solve many problems of product design and manufacturing processes. But the use of these software products by low-power sewing enterprises is limited due to the high cost of not only the entire system, but also its modules individually. In this regard, it is relevant to develop software applications that allow solving individual tasks of preparing sewing production. One of the important tasks of technological training of enterprises is the development of initial data for the design of the division of labor scheme, in particular, the choice of technological solutions for parts and assemblies of the product and the formation of the technological sequence of its manufacture. To automate the solution of this task, it is enough to create an application software. This paper describes the results of the work of students of Omsk State Technical University, which consist in the development of a database using Microsoft Access and the software application "Assistant Technologist". The developed application software allows you to form the technological sequence of processing the product model of the coat and costume assortment in an automated mode. The database and the application can be used independently

or integrated into modules of existing computer-aided clothing design systems, as well as in the process of training garment manufacturing technologists.

Keywords: garment industry, technological preparation of production, technological sequence of product processing, information technology, application software

Currently, various computer-aided design (CAD) systems of clothing are successfully operating at domestic enterprises, which make it possible to effectively use information technologies for collecting, transmitting, processing, accumulating, storing and presenting information, developing solutions at the pre-production stage [1-3]. As a rule, the "Technologist" module, which is part of the clothing CAD, allows you to solve many tasks of technological preparation of production, in particular, the choice of processing methods for the nodes of the designed product, the development of a technological sequence for its manufacture, the drawing up of a division of labor scheme for the sewing flow. But it should be noted that the use of these software products by small-scale sewing enterprises, as well as higher educational institutions using such systems to improve the level of training of specialists, is limited. This is primarily due to the high cost of not only the entire CAD system, but also its modules individually. In this regard, it is relevant to develop application software that allows solving individual tasks of preparing garment production, which can be used autonomously or in integration with existing clothing CAD modules [4, 5].

The choice of product processing methods and the compilation of the technological sequence of its manufacture is an integral part of the technological preparation of clothing manufacturing processes. The results of technological design determine not only the quality of the finished product, but also the efficiency of production as a whole. The use of digital technologies is effective for solving these problems. The practical purpose of this study is to develop applied software for technological purposes, consisting of a database (DB), a

database management system (DBMS) and a user application that allows a garment manufacturing technologist to interact with a database and form an automated technological sequence of product processing in accordance with its design and technological solution.

The database should contain a directory of technological indivisible operations for processing products of various design and technological solutions. The software application for the user to work with the database should be inexpensive, technically uncomplicated, with a "friendly" interface and minimal hardware requirements, as well as providing for the possibility of editing the database for specific production conditions.

The educational purpose of the work is to teach future specialists how to use software tools, as well as independently develop information systems for various purposes [6, 7].

Materials and methods of research

In order to achieve this goal, students of the training direction 29.03.01 Technology of light industry products of Omsk State Technical University were tasked with developing application software for automating the formation of a technological sequence of product processing in accordance with its design and technological solution using the example of a women's demi-season coat. The developed software includes a database, a DBMS and an Assistant Technologist software application.

The work was carried out as part of the research work of students in the process of mastering the disciplines of the educational program: "Design activity", "Technology of sewing products", "Design of sewing production processes". To solve the tasks, methods of information analysis and synthesis, as well as methods of database design and management were used.

As a result of the analysis of the processing stages and possible design and technological solutions of the products of the specified range, the variety and

content of the structural elements of the manufacturing process were revealed, and a seven-digit coding system was proposed. The first two digits from 00 to 99 indicate the processing stage, the part of the product, the third digit from 1 to 9 is the name of the node, the fourth digit from 1 to 9 is the type of node, the fifth digit from 1 to 9 is the model feature of the node, the sixth digit from 1 to 9 is the design and technological feature of the node, the seventh digit from 1 to 2 – the presence or absence of a finishing stitch. For example, the code 03.6.3.1.1.1 stands for as follows: the first pair of digits 03 is the processing of the shelf, the third digit 6 is the processing of pockets, the fourth digit 3 is the processing of slash pockets, the fifth digit 1 is the processing of slash pockets with a leaflet, the sixth digit 1 is the processing of slash pockets with a leaflet with turn-in ends, the last 1 is without finishing stitching along the line of entry into the pocket. Zero in the code means that there is no encoding feature. For example, the code 16.4.0.0.1.0 means: the first two digits 16 – processing of finishing elements, the third 4 – processing of the edge of the flying yoke, the fourth, fifth, seventh digits 0 – absence of a coding sign, the sixth 1 – processing of the edge of the flying yoke with a lining. In accordance with the proposed coding system, the technological filling of the database was performed.

Microsoft Access DBMS is selected because it is included in office programs and does not require the installation of additional software products. Microsoft Access is a relational database management system, the structure is shown in Figure 1. Standard elements of the relational data model and the forms of their designation were used. For example, the relationship diagram (relationship header) is a list of attribute names: "Operations" (ID – key, Name Operations – operation name, Number Collections – operation number, Type Work – type of work, Level Work – category of work, Time Work – duration of operation, Pictures – processing scheme in the form of a picture).

Fig. 1. Database structure

The structure of this database includes 2 user tables "Operations", which contains the technological sequence, and "Stage" (stages of product processing). The tables "Type Works" (types of work) and "Equipment" (equipment) depend on these tables, are systemic and serve for the normal functioning of the database; the tables "Used Operations" (used operations), "Used Equipment" (used equipment) – serve to avoid the links "infinity to infinity." Relationship 1:∞ means that one record of the main table corresponds to several records of the auxiliary table.

The developed database is accompanied by the program "Assistant Technologist" (Assistant technologist), written in the Delphi environment. With its help, the technologist of the sewing enterprise can make changes to the contents of the database, as well as extract information from it for further work. The program contains a variety of technological indivisible operations with their characteristics for each structural element of the technological process of manufacturing a women's demi-season coat and assembly schemes of nodes in the form of drawings. The program automatically calculates the total time to complete each stage of processing and the designed product as a whole. From the program, you can print out the technological sequence of processing a women's demi-season coat as a whole and by stages, it can be exported to Excel, where you can continue working with the information received.

When you log into the Assistant Technologist program, the main dialog box appears, in which the product processing steps and a horizontal menu bar are located in the left corner of the upper part of the window, and in the lower right corner there are two buttons "load tree" (to display information on the screen) and "print" (Fig. 2). When selecting a certain structural element in the upper part of the window – a stage corresponding to the technological process of manufacturing a specific model in accordance with its design and technological solution, a technological sequence of processing this stage appears in the lower part of the window in the form of a list of technological indivisible operations with their characteristics, in the right part of the window - visualization of the processing method in the form of a diagram. Under the technological sequence at the bottom of the window, the complexity of processing a structural element is automatically calculated.

Fig. 2. The main window of the Assistant Technologist program

and the

Fig. 3. The "Directories" tab – "Stag

Fig. 4. An example of adding images

Fig. 5. The Excel window

The menu bar is represented by four tabs: "File", "Directories", "Operations" and "Help". The Directories tab is used to add, edit or delete information; it

contains three components: "Types of work", "Operations", "Stages". There are types of work: manual, machine, ironing, etc. The reference book "Stages" lists the structural elements of the technological process of manufacturing a women's demi-season coat, taking into account the structural and technological diversity of products. The Operations directory contains technological indivisible operations related to each structural element (Fig. 3). In addition, this window displays a drawing of the processing scheme of the selected structural element. An example of uploading drawings to the database is shown in Fig. 4.

To obtain the technological sequence of processing the entire product, it is necessary to select the structural elements present in this model from the list of "Stages of product processing" according to the sketch of the model and print the processing of all structural elements. If necessary, further work with the received information can be exported to Excel (Fig. 5), where you can edit the received information to a ready-made form.

The results of the study and their discussion

As a result of working with the Assistant Technologist software application, the technologist generates initial information for the design of the product manufacturing process in the form of a list of technological indivisible operations with their characteristics in an automated mode, selecting the appropriate structural elements of the process from the database. Additionally, the user receives assembly diagrams of nodes in the form of drawings, as well as the total time of operations. After formatting the table with the technological sequence of processing the designed product in Excel format, actions can be taken to develop a division of labor **scheme**.

Conclusion

One of the promising approaches to improving the preparation of production and the design of technological processes is the use of computers. The high cost of CAD and certain difficulties with mastering the system limit the possibilities of

its wide application. Individual training tasks, including technological ones, are designed to be solved by application software, which is inexpensive and easy to use. The developed software, consisting of a database, a DBMS and an Assistant Technologist application, allows you to obtain the technological sequence of processing the designed product in tabular form, assembly diagrams of nodes in the form of drawings and the total time of operations.

Since the possession of IT technologies is becoming the main factor in the competitiveness of graduates, this work will allow them to learn automated process design and independently develop information systems for technological purposes.

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